

Modeling and Analysis of Multi-tier Networks Using Inhomogeneous Poisson Point Processes

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Abstract—In this paper, we introduce a new methodology for modeling and analyzing downlink cellular networks, where the Base Stations (BSs) constitute a motion-invariant Point Process (PP) that exhibits some degree of interactions among the points, i.e., spatial inhibition (repulsion) or spatial aggregation (clustering). The proposed approach is based on the theory of Inhomogeneous Poisson PPs (I-PPPs) and is referred to as Inhomogeneous Double Thinning (IDT) approach. This proposed approach consists of approximating the original motion-invariant PP with an equivalent PP that is made of the superposition of two conditionally independent I-PPPs. Based on the IDT approach, we propose the mathematical framework of the system model that accounts for the multi-tier network deployments. The accuracy of the IDT approach is substantiated with the aid of empirical data for the spatial distribution of the BSs.

Index Terms—Inhomogeneous Point Processes, Stochastic Geometry, Multi-tier network, Spatial Inhibition/Aggregation

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the Poisson Point Processes (PPPs) has been extensively applying in wireless communications for modeling and analyzing the performance of emerging cellular network architectures [1]. Notable examples include, Heterogeneous Cellular Networks (HCNs) [2], Multiple-Input-Multiple-Output (MIMO) HCNs [3], [4], millimeter-wave cellular HCNs [5]. Although modeling cellular networks by using PPPs has the advantage in analysis and optimization for the mathematical tractability, however, practical cellular networks exhibit some spatial correlation between BSs, like repulsion and clustering [6]- [11].

A. Inhomogeneous Double Thinning: Contribution

The proposed approach based on I-PPPs is referred to as Inhomogeneous Double Thinning (IDT) approach. The contributions made by this paper are as follows.

- We propose I-PPPs for modeling the spatial correlation inherently present in cellular network deployments. The IDT approach is general and flexible enough for modeling cellular networks that exhibit spatial inhibition, aggregation, and their combination.
- We introduce two distance-dependent intensity functions to create the inhomogeneities based on spatial inhibition and aggregation properties empirically observed in practical cellular networks. They are shown to yield a good trade-off between accuracy and tractability.

TABLE I: Functions used in the paper.

Symbol/Function	Definition
$\mathbb{E}\{\cdot\}, \mathbb{1}(\cdot)$	Expectation operator, Indicator function
$\mathbb{E}^{!x}\{\cdot\}$	Expectation under the reduced Palm measure
$f_X(\cdot)$	Probability density function of X
$\mathcal{M}_{1,X}(\cdot)$	Laplace functional conditioned on X
${}_2F_1(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot, \cdot)$	Gauss hypergeometric function
$\max\{x, y\}, \min\{x, y\}$	Maximum and Minmum between x and y
$(a_F, b_F, c_F), (a_K, b_K, c_K)$	Parameters of the approximating I-PPPs

- Based on the IDT approach, a new tractable mathematical expression of the coverage probability of multi-tier cellular networks is introduced. The accuracy of the IDT approach is substantiated via empirical data for the locations of cellular BSs.

B. Paper Organization and Structure

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, the system model is introduced. In Section III, the IDT approach is illustrated. In Section IV, the multi-tier cellular network is depicted. The mathematical framework of the coverage is derived in Section V. In Section VI, the IDT approach is substantiated via empirical data and simulations. Finally, Section VII concludes this paper.

Notation: The main symbols and functions used in this paper are reported in Table I.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

In this section, the network model is introduced. We focus on single-tier cellular networks for simplification, by assuming an unbounded path-loss model and neglecting spatial blockages [12].

A. Cellular Networks Modeling

A downlink cellular network is considered. The BSs are modeled as points of a motion-invariant PP, denoted by Ψ_{BS} , of density λ_{BS} . The BSs' locations are denoted by $x \in \Psi_{BS} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^2$. The Mobile Terminals (MTs) are distributed independently of each other and uniformly at random in \mathbb{R}^2 . The density of MTs is denoted by λ_{MT} . Thanks to the assumption of motion-invariance, the PP of BSs is stationary and isotropic. As a result, the mathematical frameworks are developed for the typical MT, denoted by MT_0 , that is located at the origin. The BS serving MT_0 is denoted by BS_0 . Its location is denoted by $x_0 \in \Psi_{BS}$. The cell association criterion

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{f}_{L_0^{(F)}}(\xi) &= \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{1/\gamma} \frac{1}{\gamma\xi} \Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}}^{(1)}\left(\mathcal{B}\left(0, \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{1/\gamma}\right)\right) \exp\left(-\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}}\left(\mathcal{B}\left(0, \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa}\right)^{1/\gamma}\right)\right)\right) \\ \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{1, L_0^{(F)}}(\xi; T) &= \exp\left(-\int_{\xi}^{+\infty} \left(1 + \frac{z}{T\xi}\right)^{-1} \left(\frac{z}{\kappa}\right)^{1/\gamma} \frac{1}{\gamma z} \Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}}^{(1)}\left(\mathcal{B}\left(0, \left(\frac{z}{\kappa}\right)^{1/\gamma}\right)\right) dz\right)\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

is introduced in Section II-C. The BSs and MTs are equipped with a single omnidirectional antenna. Each BS transmits with a constant power denoted by P_{tx} . A fully loaded assumption is considered, i.e., $\lambda_{\text{BS}} \gg \lambda_{\text{MT}}$, which implies that all the BSs are active and have MTs to serve. All available BSs transmit on the same physical channel as BS_0 . The PP of interfering BSs is denoted by $\Psi_{\text{BS}}^{(1)}$. Besides the inter-cell interference, Gaussian noise with power σ_{N}^2 is taken into account as well.

B. Channel Modeling

For each BS-to-MT₀ link, path-loss and fast-fading are considered. Shadowing is not explicitly considered for simplicity, but it can be taken into account by using the approach in [12]. All BS-to-MT₀ links are assumed to be mutually independent and identically distributed (i.i.d.).

a) Path-Loss: Consider a generic BS whose location is $x \in \Psi_{\text{BS}}$. The path-loss is defined as $l(x) = \kappa \|x\|^\gamma$, where κ and $\gamma > 2$ are the path-loss constant and the path-loss slope (exponent).

b) Fast-Fading: Consider a generic BS-to-MT₀ link. The power gain due to small-scale fading is assumed to follow an exponential distribution with mean m . Without loss of generality, $m = 1$ is assumed. The power gain of a generic BS-to-MT₀ link is denoted by g_x for $x \in \Psi_{\text{BS}}$.

C. Cell Association Criterion

A cell association based on the highest average received power is assumed. Let $x \in \Psi_{\text{BS}}$ be the location of a generic BS. The location, x_0 , of the serving BS, BS_0 , is obtained as follows:

$$x_0 = \arg \max_{x \in \Psi_{\text{BS}}} \{1/l(x)\} = \arg \max_{x \in \Psi_{\text{BS}}} \{1/L_x\} \quad (1)$$

where $L_x = l(x)$ is a shorthand. As for the intended link, $L_0 = l(x_0) = \min_{x \in \Psi_{\text{BS}}} \{L_x\}$ holds.

D. Coverage Probability

The performance metric of interest is the coverage probability, P_{cov} , that is defined as follows:

$$P_{\text{cov}} = \Pr \left\{ \frac{P_{\text{tx}} g_0 / L_0}{\sigma_{\text{N}}^2 + \sum_{x \in \Psi_{\text{BS}}^{(1)}} P_{\text{tx}} g_x / L_x} > T \right\} \quad (2)$$

where $\Psi_{\text{BS}}^{(1)} = \Psi_{\text{BS}} \setminus x_0$.

We focus our attention on the coverage probability because it corresponds to the complementary cumulative distribution function of the SINR, and, thus, it completely characterizes the statistical properties of the SINR. Other relevant performance metrics, e.g., the average rate, the potential spectral efficiency, and the local delay, that depend on the SINR can be directly obtained from the coverage probability.

III. THE INHOMOGENEOUS DOUBLE THINNING APPROACH

The approach that we propose for computing P_{cov} lies in introducing an equivalent abstraction for the system model in Section II-A that is based on I-PPPs. For ease of exposition, we first introduce the equivalent network model in general terms and then describe the IDT approach. The equivalent network model, in particular, is constituted by two I-PPPs, $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}$ and $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}$, which are constructed in a very special way and with the only purpose of approximating the original motion-invariant PP from the point of view of the typical user.

A. Cellular Networks Abstraction Modeling Based on I-PPPs

We consider the same system model as in Section II-A with a single exception: The BSs are modeled as the points of two *independent* isotropic I-PPPs, denoted by $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}$ and $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}$, with intensity measures $\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}}(\cdot)$ and $\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}}(\cdot)$, respectively. Since I-PPPs are non-stationary, we are interested in computing the coverage probability of a *probe* (or specific) MT that is located at the origin. The BS serving the probe MT is assumed to belong to $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}$ and the interfering BSs are assumed to belong to $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}$. More precisely, by considering the same cell association criterion as in Section II-C, the serving BS and the I-PPP, $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(1)}$, of interfering BSs can be formulated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}x_0^{(F)} &= \arg \max_{x \in \Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}} \{1/l(x)\} \\ \Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(1)} &= \Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}(x_0^{(F)}) = \left\{ x \in \Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)} : l(x) > L_0^{(F)} = l(x_0^{(F)}) \right\}\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

In the proposed network model, which is based on I-PPPs and the cell association constraints defined in (3), the coverage probability of the probe MT at the origin can be formulated as:

$$\tilde{P}_{\text{cov}}^{(o)} = \Pr \left\{ \frac{P_{\text{tx}} g_0 / L_0^{(F)}}{\sigma_{\text{N}}^2 + \sum_{x \in \Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(1)}} P_{\text{tx}} g_x / l(x)} > T \right\} \quad (4)$$

where the superscript (o) highlights that (4) holds for the probe MT at the origin.

The coverage probability, $\tilde{P}_{\text{cov}}^{(o)}$, in (4) is explicitly formulated in the following lemma.

Lemma 1: An analytical expression of the coverage probability is as follows:

$$\tilde{P}_{\text{cov}}^{(o)} = \int_0^{+\infty} \exp(-\xi T \sigma_{\text{N}}^2 / P_{\text{tx}}) \tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{1, L_0^{(F)}}(\xi; T) \tilde{f}_{L_0^{(F)}}(\xi) d\xi \quad (5)$$

where $\tilde{f}_{L_0^{(F)}}(\cdot)$ is the PDF of $L_0^{(F)}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{M}}_{1, L_0^{(F)}}(\cdot; \cdot)$ is the Laplace functional of $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(1)}$ as in (6) and $\Lambda_{(\cdot)}^{(1)}(\mathcal{B}(0, r)) = d\Lambda_{(\cdot)}(\mathcal{B}(0, r))/dr$ is the first-order derivative of the intensity measure.

Proof: It follows by applying the approach as in [12]. \square

B. IDT Approach: Proposed Intensity Measures of the I-PPPs

The intensity measure of an I-PPP is determined by the intensity function [13, Sec. 2.2]. Let $\lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}(\cdot)$ and $\lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}(\cdot)$ be the intensity functions of $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}$ and $\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}$ which are distance-dependent and angular-independent. The following holds:

$$\begin{aligned}\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}}(\mathcal{B}(0, r)) &= 2\pi \int_0^r \lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}(\zeta) \zeta d\zeta \\ \Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}}(\mathcal{B}(0, r)) &= 2\pi \int_0^r \lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}(\zeta) \zeta d\zeta\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

We propose different intensity functions for PPPs that exhibit spatial inhibition and aggregation. Let $(\check{\alpha}_F, \check{b}_F, \check{c}_F)$ and $(\check{\alpha}_K, \check{b}_K, \check{c}_K)$ be two triplets of non-negative real numbers.

a) *Spatial Inhibition:* $\check{c}_F \geq \check{b}_F \geq 1$ and $\check{b}_K \leq \check{c}_K \leq 1$. The following intensities are proposed:

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}(r) &= \lambda_{\text{BS}} \check{c}_F \min\{\check{\alpha}_F / \check{c}_F r + \check{b}_F / \check{c}_F, 1\}, \\ \lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}(r) &= \lambda_{\text{BS}} \min\{\check{\alpha}_K r + \check{b}_K, \check{c}_K\}\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

b) *Spatial Aggregation:* $\hat{c}_F \leq \hat{b}_F \leq 1$ and $\hat{b}_K \geq \hat{c}_K \geq 1$. The following intensities are proposed:

$$\begin{aligned}\lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(F)}(r) &= \lambda_{\text{BS}} \max\{-\hat{\alpha}_F r + \hat{b}_F, \hat{c}_F\}, \\ \lambda_{\text{BS}}^{(K)}(r) &= \lambda_{\text{BS}} \hat{b}_K \max\{-\hat{\alpha}_K / \hat{b}_K r + 1, \hat{c}_K / \hat{b}_K\}\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

For ease of writing, the intensity measures of PPPs with spatial repulsion and clustering are denoted by $\Lambda_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(\cdot)}}(\cdot; \check{\alpha}_{(\cdot)}, \check{b}_{(\cdot)}, \check{c}_{(\cdot)}) = \check{\Lambda}_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(\cdot)}}(\cdot)$.

The following lemma provides closed-form expressions for the intensity measures in (7).

Lemma 2: Let $\Upsilon(r; a, b, c)$ and $\Upsilon^{(1)}(r; a, b, c)$ be defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}\Upsilon(r; a, b, c) &= 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \left((a/3)r^3 + (b/2)r^2 \right) \mathbb{1}(r \leq (c-b)/a) \\ &\quad + 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \left((c/2)r^2 - (c-b)^3/6a^2 \right) \mathbb{1}(r > (c-b)/a) \\ \Upsilon^{(1)}(r; a, b, c) &= 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} (ar^2 + br) \mathbb{1}(r \leq (c-b)/a) \\ &\quad + 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} cr \mathbb{1}(r > (c-b)/a)\end{aligned}\quad (10)$$

where $\Upsilon^{(1)}(r; a, b, c) = d\Upsilon(r; a, b, c)/dr$ is the first-order derivative of $\Upsilon(r; \cdot, \cdot, \cdot)$.

The intensity measures in (7) can be formulated as $\check{\Lambda}_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(\cdot)}}(\mathcal{B}(0, r)) = \Upsilon(r; \check{\alpha}_{(\cdot)}, \check{b}_{(\cdot)}, \check{c}_{(\cdot)})$ and $\hat{\Lambda}_{\Phi_{\text{BS}}^{(\cdot)}}(\mathcal{B}(0, r)) = \Upsilon(r; -\hat{\alpha}_{(\cdot)}, \hat{b}_{(\cdot)}, \hat{c}_{(\cdot)})$ for PPPs that exhibit repulsion and clus-

tering, respectively. The first-order derivatives of the intensity measures have same features.

Proof: It follows by inserting (8) and (9) in (7) and solving the integrals. \square

IV. MULTI-TIER CELLULAR NETWORKS

In this section, we consider a two-tier cellular network. The tiers are denoted by T1 and T2. The BSs of tiers T1 and T2 belong to two independent and motion-invariant PPPs that are denoted by Ψ_{T1} and Ψ_{T2} , respectively. The system model is the same as in Section II for single-tier cellular networks, with a few exceptions. Let $x \in \Psi_{\mathcal{T}}$ be the location of a BS of tier $\mathcal{T} \in \{\text{T1}, \text{T2}\}$. The path-loss at location x is $l_{\mathcal{T}}(x) = \kappa_{\mathcal{T}} \|x\|^{\gamma_{\mathcal{T}}}$, where $\kappa_{\mathcal{T}}$ and $\gamma_{\mathcal{T}}$ are the path-loss constant and slope of tier \mathcal{T} similar to Section II-B. The transmit power of tier \mathcal{T} is $P_{\mathcal{T}} = \delta_{\mathcal{T}} P_{\text{tx}}$, where $\delta_{\mathcal{T}} \geq 0$. A similar notation is employed for the other system parameters introduced in Section II. The cell association criterion is based on the highest average received power. More precisely, let $x_{\mathcal{T},0}$ be the location of the BS of tier \mathcal{T} that provides the smallest path-loss to the typical MT and that is computed by using (1). Then, the location of the serving BS of the typical MT of the two-tier cellular network is $x_{\text{T1},0}$ if $P_{\text{T1}}/l_{\text{T1}}(x_{\text{T1},0}) \geq P_{\text{T2}}/l_{\text{T2}}(x_{\text{T2},0})$ and $x_{\text{T2},0}$ otherwise. For ease of writing, we introduce the shorthand $\bar{\kappa}_{\mathcal{T}} = \kappa_{\mathcal{T}}/\delta_{\mathcal{T}}$ for $\mathcal{T} \in \{\text{T1}, \text{T2}\}$.

We apply the IDT approach for modeling the locations of the BSs of Ψ_{T1} and Ψ_{T2} . In particular, each motion-invariant PP is approximated by using two I-PPPs, which, similar to Section III, are denoted by $(\Phi_{\text{T1}}^{(F)}, \Phi_{\text{T1}}^{(K)})$ and $(\Phi_{\text{T2}}^{(F)}, \Phi_{\text{T2}}^{(K)})$. The parameters of each pair of I-PPPs are obtained as described in Section III. In simple terms, each motion-invariant PP is approximated, from the typical MT's standpoint, with two I-PPPs as if it was the only tier of the cellular network. The BS of tier $\mathcal{T} \in \{\text{T1}, \text{T2}\}$ that provides that smallest path-loss among all the BSs of tier \mathcal{T} and the corresponding I-PPP of conditionally independent interfering BSs are defined similar to (3), and are denoted by $x_{\mathcal{T},0}^{(F)} \in \Phi_{\mathcal{T}}^{(F)}$ and $\Phi_{\mathcal{T}}^{(I)} = \Phi_{\mathcal{T}}^{(I)}(x_{\mathcal{T},0}^{(F)}) \subseteq \Phi_{\mathcal{T}}^{(K)}$. Similar to (4), the coverage probability of a two-tier cellular network is $\tilde{P}_{\text{cov}}^{(o)} = \Pr\{\text{SINR} > T\}$, where SINR can be denoted as (11).

V. TRACTABLE ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK OF THE COVERAGE PROBABILITY

With the aid of the IDT approach, we introduce a new tractable expression of the coverage for cellular networks

$$\begin{aligned}\text{SINR} &= \frac{\left(P_{\text{T1}} g_{\text{T1},0} / l_{\text{T1}}(x_{\text{T1},0}^{(F)}) \right) \mathbb{1}(P_{\text{T1}}/l_{\text{T1}}(x_{\text{T1},0}) \geq P_{\text{T2}}/l_{\text{T2}}(x_{\text{T2},0}))}{\sigma_{\text{N}}^2 + \sum_{x \in \Phi_{\text{T1}}^{(I)}(x_{\text{T1},0}^{(F)})} P_{\text{T1}} g_{\text{T1},x} / l_{\text{T1}}(x) + \sum_{x \in \Phi_{\text{T2}}^{(I)}(x_{\text{T2},0}^{(F)})} P_{\text{T2}} g_{\text{T2},x} / l_{\text{T2}}(x) + P_{\text{T2}} g_{\text{T2},x} / l_{\text{T2}}(x_{\text{T2},0}^{(F)})} \\ &\quad + \frac{\left(P_{\text{T2}} g_{\text{T2},0} / l_{\text{T2}}(x_{\text{T2},0}^{(F)}) \right) \mathbb{1}(P_{\text{T2}}/l_{\text{T2}}(x_{\text{T2},0}) > P_{\text{T1}}/l_{\text{T1}}(x_{\text{T1},0}))}{\sigma_{\text{N}}^2 + \sum_{x \in \Phi_{\text{T2}}^{(I)}(x_{\text{T2},0}^{(F)})} P_{\text{T2}} g_{\text{T2},x} / l_{\text{T2}}(x) + \sum_{x \in \Phi_{\text{T1}}^{(I)}(x_{\text{T1},0}^{(F)})} P_{\text{T1}} g_{\text{T1},x} / l_{\text{T1}}(x) + P_{\text{T1}} g_{\text{T1},x} / l_{\text{T1}}(x_{\text{T1},0}^{(F)})}\end{aligned}\quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{P}_{\text{cov}}^{(\circ)} &= \int_0^{\Theta_{T1}} \left(\int_{\xi_1}^{\Theta_{T2}} e^{-\xi_1 T \sigma_N^2 / P_{\text{tx}}} (1 + T(\xi_1 / \xi_2))^{-1} e^{-\mathcal{W}_1(\xi_1, \xi_2)} \mathcal{U}_{T2,0}(\xi_2) d\xi_2 \right) \mathcal{U}_{T1,0}(\xi_1) d\xi_1 \\ &+ \int_0^{\Theta_{T2}} \left(\int_{\xi_2}^{\Theta_{T1}} e^{-\xi_1 T \sigma_N^2 / P_{\text{tx}}} (1 + T(\xi_2 / \xi_1))^{-1} e^{-\mathcal{W}_2(\xi_1, \xi_2)} \mathcal{U}_{T1,0}(\xi_1) d\xi_1 \right) \mathcal{U}_{T2,0}(\xi_2) d\xi_2 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

whose BSs exhibit spatial inhibition or aggregation. Based on *Lemma 2*, the analysis of network models is unified by considering a generic triplet of parameters $(a_{(\cdot)}, b_{(\cdot)}, c_{(\cdot)})$ and by setting $(a_{(\cdot)}, b_{(\cdot)}, c_{(\cdot)}) = (\check{a}_{(\cdot)}, \check{b}_{(\cdot)}, \check{c}_{(\cdot)})$ and $(a_{(\cdot)}, b_{(\cdot)}, c_{(\cdot)}) = (-\hat{a}_{(\cdot)}, \hat{b}_{(\cdot)}, \hat{c}_{(\cdot)})$ for PPs that exhibit spatial inhibition and aggregation, respectively.

The following theorem provides a tractable expression of $\tilde{P}_{\text{cov}}^{(\circ)}$ in (4). Two case studies are considered: i) the network is infinitely large and ii) the network has a finite size whose radius is R_A . The second case study is useful for comparing the analytical frameworks against estimates obtained by using empirical data, especially for small values of the path-loss exponent. This is because it is not possible, in many cases, to obtain or generate data sets for very large regions.

Theorem 1: In two-tier cellular networks, $\tilde{P}_{\text{cov}}^{(\circ)}$ in (11) can be formulated in (12).

where $\mathcal{T} \in \{T1, T2\}$, $\Theta_{\mathcal{T}} \rightarrow \infty$ and $\Theta_{\mathcal{T}} = \bar{\kappa}_{\mathcal{T}} R_A^{\gamma_{\mathcal{T}}}$ for infinite-size and finite-size networks, respectively, $\mathcal{W}_1(\xi_1, \xi_2) = \mathcal{S}_{T1}(\xi_1, \xi_1) + \mathcal{S}_{T2}(\xi_2, \xi_1)$, $\mathcal{W}_2(\xi_1, \xi_2) = \mathcal{S}_{T1}(\xi_1, \xi_2) + \mathcal{S}_{T2}(\xi_2, \xi_2)$, and the rest of the functions are defined in (13) for $\mathcal{T} \in \{T1, T2\}$.

Proof: The proof is omitted due to space limitations. \square

VI. NUMERICAL AND SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we illustrate numerical results that substantiate the applicability of the IDT approach for modeling and

analyzing practical cellular network deployments. The network deployments considered in our study are reported in Table III. The simulation setup is summarized in Table IV.

The numerical results are reported in Figs. 1, by considering multi-tier cellular network models. There are three curves are shown in Figs. 1: i) the curve labelled ‘‘Empirical (R)’’ is obtained by generating the data sets listed in Table III by using R [14], as described in Table IV. The data sets are imported in Matlab and the coverage is obtained through Monte Carlo simulations. The data sets of the GPP are obtained by using the simulation method in [15]; ii) the curve labelled ‘‘PPP-IDT’’ is obtained by using the IDT approach with the triplets of parameters provided in Tables VI. Monte Carlo simulations are obtained in Matlab by using the algorithm reported in Table V. The analytical frameworks are computed with Mathematica; and iii) the curve labelled ‘‘PPP-H’’ corresponds to the benchmark cellular network deployments where the BSs are distributed according to H-PPPs. The solid lines are obtained from analytical frameworks in *Theorems 1*.

Based on the result in Figs. 1, we evince that the IDT approach is accurate, tractable and capable of reproducing the spatial interactions of several PPs widely used for modeling the locations of BSs in multi-tier cellular networks.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have introduced a new tractable approach for modeling and analyzing cellular networks where the lo-

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{U}_{\text{IN}}(\xi) &= 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \left(\frac{a_{\text{F}}}{\gamma\xi} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa} \right)^{3/\gamma} + \frac{b_{\text{F}}}{\gamma\xi} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa} \right)^{2/\gamma} \right) \exp \left(-2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \left(\frac{a_{\text{F}}}{3} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa} \right)^{3/\gamma} + \frac{b_{\text{F}}}{2} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa} \right)^{2/\gamma} \right) \right) \\ \mathcal{U}_{\text{OUT}}(\xi) &= 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \frac{c_{\text{F}}}{\gamma\xi} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa} \right)^{2/\gamma} \exp \left(-2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \left(\frac{c_{\text{F}}}{2} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa} \right)^{2/\gamma} - \frac{(c_{\text{F}} - b_{\text{F}})^3}{6a_{\text{F}}^2} \right) \right) \\ \mathcal{I}_1(\xi) &= \frac{a_{\text{K}} d_{\text{K}}^{\frac{3}{2}}}{3} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{3}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{3}{\gamma}, -\frac{\kappa}{T\xi} d_{\text{K}}^{\gamma} \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^{\gamma}), \quad \mathcal{I}_2(\xi) = \frac{b_{\text{K}} d_{\text{K}}^{\frac{2}{2}}}{2} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{\kappa}{T\xi} d_{\text{K}}^{\gamma} \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^{\gamma}) \\ \mathcal{I}_3(\xi) &= -\frac{a_{\text{K}}}{3} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa} \right)^{3/\gamma} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{3}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{3}{\gamma}, -\frac{1}{T} \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^{\gamma}), \quad \mathcal{I}_4(\xi) = -\frac{b_{\text{K}}}{2} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa} \right)^{2/\gamma} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{1}{T} \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^{\gamma}) \\ \mathcal{I}_5(\xi) &= -\frac{c_{\text{K}} d_{\text{K}}^{\frac{2}{2}}}{2} \left(1 - {}_2F_1 \left(1, -\frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 - \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{T\xi}{\kappa} d_{\text{K}}^{-\gamma} \right) \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^{\gamma}), \quad \mathcal{I}_6(\xi) = -\frac{c_{\text{K}}}{2} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa} \right)^{2/\gamma} \left(1 - {}_2F_1 \left(1, -\frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 - \frac{2}{\gamma}, -T \right) \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \geq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^{\gamma}) \\ \mathcal{I}_7(\xi) &= \frac{c_{\text{K}} R_{\text{A}}^2}{2} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{\kappa}{T\xi} R_{\text{A}}^{\gamma} \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^{\gamma}), \quad \mathcal{I}_8(\xi) = -\frac{c_{\text{K}} d_{\text{K}}^{\frac{2}{2}}}{2} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{\kappa}{T\xi} d_{\text{K}}^{\gamma} \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^{\gamma}) \\ \mathcal{I}_9(\xi) &= \frac{c_{\text{K}} R_{\text{A}}^2}{2} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{\kappa}{T\xi} R_{\text{A}}^{\gamma} \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \geq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^{\gamma}), \quad \mathcal{I}_{10}(\xi) = -\frac{c_{\text{K}}}{2} \left(\frac{\xi}{\kappa} \right)^{2/\gamma} {}_2F_1 \left(1, \frac{2}{\gamma}, 1 + \frac{2}{\gamma}, -\frac{1}{T} \right) \mathbb{1}(\xi \geq \kappa d_{\text{K}}^{\gamma}) \\ \mathcal{I}_{\infty}(\xi) &= 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \sum_{k=1}^6 \mathcal{I}_k(\xi), \quad \mathcal{I}_{R_{\text{A}}}(\xi) = 2\pi\lambda_{\text{BS}} \left(\sum_{k=1}^4 \mathcal{I}_k(\xi) + \sum_{k=7}^{10} \mathcal{I}_k(\xi) \right) \\ \Pi_{\mathcal{T}} &= \{ \kappa = \bar{\kappa}_{\mathcal{T}}, \gamma = \gamma_{\mathcal{T}}, a_{\text{F}} = a_{\mathcal{T},\text{F}}, b_{\text{F}} = b_{\mathcal{T},\text{F}}, c_{\text{F}} = c_{\mathcal{T},\text{F}} \} \\ \mathcal{U}_{T,0}(\xi) &= \mathcal{U}_{\text{IN}}(\xi; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}) \mathbb{1}(\xi \leq \bar{\kappa}_{\mathcal{T}} ((c_{\mathcal{T},\text{F}} - b_{\mathcal{T},\text{F}}) / a_{\mathcal{T},\text{F}})^{\gamma_{\mathcal{T}}}) + \mathcal{U}_{\text{OUT}}(\xi; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}) \mathbb{1}(\xi \geq \bar{\kappa}_{\mathcal{T}} ((c_{\mathcal{T},\text{F}} - b_{\mathcal{T},\text{F}}) / a_{\mathcal{T},\text{F}})^{\gamma_{\mathcal{T}}}) \\ \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{T}}(x, y; \Theta \rightarrow \infty) &= \mathcal{I}_1(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = T = Ty/x) + \mathcal{I}_2(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = T = Ty/x) + \mathcal{I}_3(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = Ty/x) \\ &+ \mathcal{I}_4(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = Ty/x) + \mathcal{I}_5(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = T = Ty/x) + \mathcal{I}_6(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = Ty/x) \\ \mathcal{S}_{\mathcal{T}}(x, y; \Theta_{\mathcal{T}} = \bar{\kappa}_{\mathcal{T}} R_{\text{A}}^{\gamma_{\mathcal{T}}}) &= \mathcal{I}_1(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = T = Ty/x) + \mathcal{I}_2(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = T = Ty/x) + \mathcal{I}_3(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = Ty/x) \\ &+ \mathcal{I}_4(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = Ty/x) + \mathcal{I}_7(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = T = Ty/x) + \mathcal{I}_8(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = T = Ty/x) \\ &+ \mathcal{I}_9(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = T = Ty/x) + \mathcal{I}_{10}(x; \Pi_{\mathcal{T}}, T = Ty/x) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

TABLE III: Empirical PPs. Their parameters are defined in the references.

Point Process	Parameters
DPP-Cauchy [?] (Houston)	$\lambda_{BS} = 0.4490$ BS/km ² , $\alpha = 1.558$, $\mu = 3.424$, Area = 16×16 km ²
Lattice PP	ISD=100m
GPP [9] (Urban, $\beta = 0.900$)	$\lambda_{BS} = 31.56$ BS/km ² , Area = $3.784^2 \pi$ km ² , $\gamma = 3.5$

TABLE IV: Setup of parameters (unless otherwise stated).

Parameter	Value ($k = \times 1000$)
γ	3.5
$\kappa = (4\pi f_c / 3 \cdot 10^8)^2$	$f_c = 2.1$ GHz
σ_N^2	0 Watt (interference limited)
P_{tx}	1 Watt
λ_{BS}	$1 / (\pi R_{cell}^2)$ BSs/km ²
Two-tier network	$\delta_{T1} = \delta_{T2} = 1$ $\tau_{T1} = \tau_{T2} = 1$ $\gamma_{T1} = \gamma_{T2} = \gamma$
Functions for sim. in R	dppCauchy
Simulations of GPPs	[15, Proposition 4.3]
Simulations of other PPs	Based on definition [14]
Number of realizations	DPP: 100k, GPP: 10k
Number of realizations	Lattice: 10k

Fig. 1: P_{cov} of DPP-Cauchy (Houston) & GPP (Urban, $\beta = 0.9$) and Square-Lattice (ISD = 100 m) & GPP (Urban, $\beta = 0.9$). Setup: $\gamma = 3.5$.

cations of the BSs exhibit some degree of spatial interaction. The proposed IDT approach is based on the theory of I-PPPs, and it is shown to be tractable and insightful. Tractability and accuracy have been substantiated by using several data sets for the locations of cellular BSs that are available in the literature. The IDT approach may be applied in different ways to simplify the analysis and optimization of cellular networks. A non-exhaustive list of potential uses for system-level analysis is the following. In conclusion, we believe that the IDT approach may have wide applicability to the modeling and design of cellular networks, e.g., to study the advantages and limitations of emerging radio access technologies by taking the spatial interactions of practical network topologies into account.

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